

ANALYSIS OF FACTORS AFFECTING THE LEVEL OF STRESS AMONG WOMEN EMPLOYEES

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ABSTRACT

Women have been making a significant contribution to modern Indian society in various fields, including politics, education, business, social services, arts and culture, sports, aerospace, journalism and media etc., Work life balance is the time given by women between personal work and office work, if it is balanced well both physical and mental health will be normal. Sometimes women has to face unnecessary stress at work place due to poor administrations, misunderstandings, excess of work over the normal time etc., indicates attentions should be given by the organization to cope with these stress. In this context, the present study mainly deals with identifying those factors create stress among the women employees. The simple random sampling technique has used and questionnaires were used to gather the data. From the analysis it is revealed that, there is an association between stress identified factors.

Keywords: Stress management, physical health, mental health, factors, banking sector.

INTRODUCTION

Women have been making a significant contribution to modern Indian society in various fields, including politics, education, business, social services, arts and culture, sports, aerospace, journalism and media etc., Work life balance is the time given by women between personal work and office work, if it is balanced well both physical and mental health will be normal. Sometimes women has to face unnecessary stress at work place due to poor administrations, misunderstandings, excess of work over the normal time etc., indicates attentions should be given by the organization to cope with these stress. Stress at workplace becomes a real problem to the organization as well as for its workers. It is the duty of the organization to understand the reasons for stress and help them to overcome it. There are some factors such The identified factors like, Extra working hours, Discrimination between employees, Delay in Promotions/increments, Gossips in the work place, No support from the Officers, Lack of co-ordination, Rigid rules and regulations, Targeting the particular employee, No encouragement for career growth, Lack of time relaxation are the various factors which creates stress among women employees, if they are under stress continuously their physical and mental health get damaged.

Workplace stress occurs when there are an imbalance between work environment and an individual ability to manage. Stress underlies such diverse conditions as psychosomatic, heart diseases and can be a major contributor to disturbances in one's emotional, social, company and family life. Stress is described as a worst condition of emotions in terms of physiological rise when people experience a negative situation in such a way that they perceive a danger to their prosperity. Women, have a lot of balancing to do between home and workplace, and balancing between social and personal requirements. In addition, the conflict of women will be all the more intense if her employer, as well as her family members held unreasonable expectations from her. Women's involvement in multiple roles had a harmful effect on their mental as well as their physical health. As stress increasing there is increasing in health problems like, heart rate, a rise in blood pressure, muscular tension, irritability and

depression. The increasing stress turns women employees to quit the job as it affects both physical and mental health. Stress not only impacts the employee's performance but also affects organizational health; due to stress women employees leave the organization.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Hutagalung & Ishak (2012) examined the predictions on sexual harassment experience towards job satisfaction and work stress among female employees at three universities in the Klang Valley, Malaysia. A questionnaire method was used to collect the primary data for this study and simple random sampling technique was used. The Analysis of Variance was used to analyse the data. From the study it is revealed that majority of women employees in public higher education institutes have experienced sexual harassments at moderate level and this study finds that sexual harassment to be a significant predictor to decrease job satisfaction and increase work stress in the workplace.

Nakka and Naidu (2016) identified level of stress among the women employees in information technology sector in Visakhapatnam city. The data has been collected by 100 women employees from the IT companies and the response details towards their stress at different work and environmental conditions. The parameters used to analyse the stress level among women employees are lack of participation in decision making, technological changes, Behavioural effects, Causative factors like, Poor working conditions, Rotating shifts, Work load/presuure.

Vijayadurai and Venkatesh (2012) identify the various causes for stresses that affect the women teachers in the college atmosphere through assessing the perceptions of the women college teachers towards their job stress in Tamilnadu. The researchers has identified the factors which causes stress are a) Heavy Work Load, b) Efforts are not Recognized, c) Lack of Clarity about Role, d) Lack of Autonomy, e) Lack of Involvement, f) Sleeping Problems, g) Sexual Problems, h) Financial problems.

Singh et.al., (2021) analysed the stress level among the women faculty member working in private colleges at Bangalore city. The data has been collected from both Undergraduate and Post graduate faculty members through the questionnaires. The researcher has used the convenience sampling method for the purpose of collecting the data. Chi-square tests has been used to analyse the data. It's proved that age of the respondent is having an association with respect to impact of stress and managing the stress. The study found that more the number of years of experience will make the women to deal with work pressure effectively and also they will be able to deal with conflict in better way. More the years of experience will make the people to handle this work pressure in better way. It's even found that most of the time respondent feel stress when do not plan the things in advance.

Anitha (2018) analyze the level of occupational stress among women employees in Coimbatore District. The researcher study has selected 100 women employees as respondents from working in functioning at Coimbatore district in Tamil Nadu by using simple random sampling technique through questionnaire method. The identified attributes of stress are a) Time management, b) Work related stress, c) Professional distress, d) Discipline and Motivation and e) Professional investment. The researcher also described about the techniques to overcome from the stress which are, Relaxation, Exercise, Recreation, Advice and Support, Professional Help and Action Planning.

Angayarkanni and Thamarai Selvi (2016) identified the impact of stress and job satisfaction among the women employees working in shopping malls in Chennai. Factor analysis has been used to assess the impact level. Environmental factors, Intellectual factors,

Organizational factors, Time factors, Health factors, Growth factors, Emotional factors and Challenging factors. From the study it is found that Occupational stress reduces the growth of organizations and also created lot of health problem. It is recommended that women should be encourage and motivate the women in order to reduce their stress at work place. Organization must begin to manage people at work differently, treating them with respect and valuing their contribution by way of continuous support, encouragement and motivation.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

It is known fact that, the stress level at work has been witnessing many deceases among the workers; especially women employees are facing serious problems at work place. This stress is very much dangerous again it creates many physical and mental related problems. It is highly challenging that balancing between work and family in any field of their choice. Stress leads to enormous problem. Stress Management is very much essential in coping the level of stress as it coordinates the both work and family. In this background the present research is oriented to know the factors causes stress and to understand the various techniques of stress management.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The present study is aims at achieving the following objectives.

1. To understand the concept of stress.
2. To identify the factors leads to stress.

HYPOTHESIS OF THE STUDY

Based on the above objectives the following hypothesis has been developed.

H0: "There is no relationship between stress and identified factors."

H1: "There is a relationship between stress and identified factors."

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study has used Descriptive Research Design for clear and precise investigation. The main aim of this research article is to analyse the stress level among the women employees working in banking sector at Mysore city. Both primary and secondary data are used to collect the data. Primary Data is employed to collect the data from the respondents. The study has framed the structured questionnaire for the purpose of collecting the primary data. Simple random sampling technique has been used. Since the population for the survey is very large, and due to time limitation a sample size of 50 is taken for the survey with help of questionnaire.

Percentage analysis and one sample t- test has been applied.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATIONS

This section includes both demographic profiles and inferential analysis of the respondents.

Table 1 showing the Age of the respondents

S. No.	Age (Scale)	Respondents	
		Number	Percentage
1	Below 25 years	13	26%
2	26-30 years	18	36%
3	31-40 years	12	24%

4	41-50 years	04	8%
5	51-60 years	03	6%
Total		50	100%

(Source: Primary Data)

The above table shows that, The majority of the respondents are belonged to the age group of 26-30 years, which stood at 36%.

Table 2 showing the qualification of the respondents

S. No.	Qualification (Ordinal)	Respondents	
		Number	Percentage
1	Graduated	28	56%
2	Post graduated	22	44%
3	Others	0	0%
Total		50	100%

(Source: Primary Data)

From the table it is observed that, out of total respondents 44% of them are post graduated.

Table 3 showing marital status of the respondents

S. No.	Status (nominal)	Respondents	
		Number	Percentage
1	Married	32	64%
2	Unmarried	14	28%
3	Divorced	04	8%
Total		50	100%

(Source: Primary Data)

The above table depicts that, 64% of the women are married for which the percentage stood at 64%.

Inferential analysis

Table 4 showing factors contributing stress among women employees

S.No.	Factors	Descriptive statistics		t-value	p-value
		Mean	SD		
1	Extra working hours	4.20	0.80	36.750	0.000
2	Discrimination between employees	4.52	0.50	63.331	0.000
3	Delay in Promotions/increments	4.58	0.49	64.957	0.000
4	Gossips in the work place	3.02	1.03	20.537	0.000
5	No support from the Officers	4.62	0.49	66.627	0.000

6	Lack of co-ordination	3.98	0.82	34.304	0.000
7	Rigid rules and regulations	4.66	0.47	68.861	0.000
8	Targeting the particular employee	4.52	0.50	63.331	0.000
9	No encouragement for career growth	4.92	0.27	126.948	0.000
10	Lack of time relaxation	4.56	0.50	64.305	0.000

(Source: Primary Data)

Table 4 showing the factors which leads to stress among the women employees, as women employees are experiencing stress at work place it is not possible for them to achieve the targets given. In fact, productivity of the employees will be reduced. There is a saying that, a happy employee will always be a productive employee. The calculated p-value is stood at 0.000 for all the factors, which is less than 5% level of significance. It indicates there is a significant relationship between identified factors and stress. The identified factors like, Extra working hours, Discrimination between employees, Delay in Promotions/increments, Gossips in the work place, No support from the Officers, Lack of co-ordination, Rigid rules and regulations, Targeting the particular employee, No encouragement for career growth, Lack of time relaxation are the various factors which creates stress among women employees, if they are under stress continuously their physical and mental health get damaged. The result of the study shows that the Null hypothesis “There is no relationship between stress and identified factors” is rejected and Alternative hypothesis “There is a relationship between stress and identified factors” is accepted.

FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

1. The above table shows that, the majority of the respondents are belonged to the age group of 26-30 years, which stood at 36%.
2. From the table it is observed that, out of total respondents 44% of them are post graduated.
3. The above table depicts that, 64% of the women are married for which the percentage stood at 64%.
4. As per the calculated mean value which is more than 4 which indicates there is a high agreement about the factors like Extra working hours (4.20), Discrimination between employees (4.52), Delay in Promotions/increments (4.58), No support from the Officers (4.62), Rigid rules and regulations (4.66), Targeting the particular employee (4.52), No encouragement for career growth (4.92) and Lack of time relaxation (4.56).
5. Since the p-value for all the variable is significant at 5% level of significance, hence the factors leads to more stress among the women employees.

CONCLUSION

Stress is certain in everyone’s life but coping with them is highly important to maintain personal and professional life. It is the duty of every sector to take care of women wellbeing. The organization has to provide healthy environment to work with utmost safety. Women are also equally contributing in nation’s economy. Women have been making a significant contribution to modern Indian society in various fields, including politics, education,

business, social services, arts and culture, sports, aerospace; journalism and media etc., There are many studies have proven that women is also one of the source helps in contributing nations' economy. If she works under pressure it is loss for both personal life and professional life. Coping with the stress and understanding the reasons for stress is most important.

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